

AVAILABILITY ACCESSIBILITY AND UTILIZATION OF INFORMATION RESOURCES
AT FEDERAL COLLEGE OF EDUCATION GIDAN MADI SOKOTO STATE

1Saleh Hussaini A., ¹Muhammad Sunusi N. And ³Mu'azu Muhammad Kafur

¹Department of Library

²Head Internal Audit

Federal College of Education Gidan Madi Sokoto State

ABSTRACT

This study focused on availability, accessibility, and utilization of information resources in Federal College of Education Gidan Madi, Sokoto state. The study adopted a descriptive survey research design. Samples were drawn from three schools within the college of education. The sample size used for the study was 155 which makes up 58% of the population of students and academic staff of the college study area. The data collected was analyzed using descriptive statistics that is the use of frequency tables and percentages. The findings revealed that, majority of the students with 66.66% (50) agreed that there are no available information resources in the library. Staff members on the other hand agreed there are available printed resources and disagreed with the availability of e-resources with 44.7(30). Accessibility: majority of the students being 60% (44) did not respond which makes it difficult to conclude. Hence, 26.66% (20) find it difficult to access the information resources. The staff members 37.31% (25) expressed dissatisfaction on website accessibility. Utilization: 32% of the students use the library for their assignments and the rest of the percentage splitted among other related activities including current happenings with the minimum of 9. 33%(7) challenges: there were number of challenges that were identified, which include slow internet speed, difficulty in finding related information,, limited computer system, poor/unstable electricity, lack of ICT skills, insufficient Database, Inadequate user ability in manipulating e-resources, limited access to e-resources, and poor networking system. Therefore, it is recommended that provision of more current information resources, adjusting to more friendly classification scheme for the printed resources, an increase in bandwidth, provision of stable power, employing trained staff on the ground to assist users, organize training and workshops on ICT, provide a more user-friendly platform, first-year students should be introduced to computer training.

Keywords: *Availability; Accessibility; Utilization; Information Resources.*

INTRODUCTION

Availability of information resource refers to the extent to which library information resources of different topics can be found in abundance by users. It cover both print and electronic information resources in the library. Therefore, availability is an adjective used to represent or qualify the readiness of information resources at a particular point in time in the library

Accessibility on the other hand represent the easiness of reading without much stress by library users of the available information resources more so, accessibility may also mean getting information resources needed within possible time without necessarily undergoing rigorous protocol or process of the library.

Utilization, connotes the extent of usage of these information resources by users. This means it is underutilized or over utilized, the level at which is being put to use for effective and efficient impact. When information resources were underutilized, then the objectives of the information resources have been defeated especially in knowledge seeking and development of the tertiary institutions in sokoto state.

The availability, accessibility, and utilization of information resources in tertiary institutions in Sokoto State are crucial factors that significantly influence the academic success and research output of students and faculty members. These resources include print materials, electronic resources, and other multimedia materials. The presence of information resources signifies its availability, but its accessibility and usability by the appropriate users at the right time determine its significance, as stated by the first law of librarianship: "Books (information) are for use." The effectiveness of any library lies in the quality of services provided to its users, which depends on how available and accessible the information resources are (Isa, 2020). Availability in this context means that information resources are present, reachable, accessible, and usable by readers. The

Cambridge Dictionary describes 'availability' as the state of being able to be purchased, utilized, or accessed, or the extent to which it is possible.

The effectiveness of any library is measured by the availability, accessibility, and usability of its information resources to users. It can be inferred that availability is the foundation of this equation; without available information resources, nothing can be accessed or used by users. Similarly, information captured and presented in the information resources needs to be accessed by users to satisfy their information needs (Nwachukwu, Abdusalami, Lucky, 2014). According to Schmidt and Vaughan (2018), the availability of information resources is a prerequisite for their effective use. They argue that if library users cannot access information resources, the resources cannot be employed optimally in teaching, learning, and research activities. The primary objective of any library is to grant access to relevant resources. The availability of information resources fosters an environment conducive to their users. Accurate and valuable library/information resources are essential to meet the diverse information requirements of the user community (Schmidt & Vaughan, 2018).

The accessibility of the information resources creates an enabling environment for its utilization. It's assumed that unless information resources are accessible to the user, it could not be used for effective teaching, learning, and research process. The main goal of any library is to provide access to its relevant resources. Only accurate and useful library/information resources satisfy the varying information needs of the user community. Akobundu (2008) asserted that accessibility of library and information resources is the ease to locating and retrieving a piece of information from the storage medium. Furthermore, Abdulkadir (2016) posited that access of information is the ability of a person to locate, retrieve, and secure the needed information. It's doubtless that when accessibility is evident readers require less effort and time to access whatever available information resources they have in mind (Mohammad 2012).

When information is accessed by library users, next is utilization. This has to do with the entirety of activities of users in trying to make information that is at the disposal of the library meaningful,

important, and applicable in their day-to-day activities. According to Uhegbu (2007) utilization of information differs from person to person and from one corporate to another because of variation of need and context of use. Alegbleye (2001) presented that utilization of information by any clientele is influenced by occupation, profession or function one performs.

The five (5) golden laws of librarianship are also good descriptors of information utilization; “Books are for use; every book has its reader; every reader has his/her book; save the time of reader; and the library is a growing organism” (Ranganathan, 1892 in Mohammad 2017). However, it is apparently paramount to stress that improving the availability, accessibility, and usability of information resources should be one of the key driving factors in any living library, which seeks to maintain its relevance to its user community.

Statement of the Problem

Access and use of information resources is a paramount aspect in information system. The information resources in conventional and modern system libraries especially some academic libraries need well organized, fixations and proper directories/pointers for accessibility and utilization of their collections. This collections in question needs to match with the needs of their users and equally available. This is however a great challenge to information service providers. As in some academic libraries, information resources are available but to access and use them could be challenging. Also, in some cases could be lack of related information resource.

It is in this view that this study is conducted with the intentional effort to investigate how to Improve Availability, Accessibility and Use of Information Resources among Staff and Student of Federal College of Education Gidan Madi, Sokoto State.

Objectives of the Study

The study was primarily designed to achieve the following objectives:

- i. To ascertain the types of information resources available in Federal College of Education Gidan Madi, Library.

- ii. To discover the extent at which information resources are accessible in the college library under study.
- iii. To find out how information resources available are used by the users of the College library under study.
- iv. To disclose the problems associated with availability, accessibility, and use of information resources in the college library under study.

Significance of the Study

The significance of this study gets root from the need to conduct it. Doubtlessly, the result of this study if rightly applied will mark the end of the current challenges associated with availability, accessibility, and use of information resources in Federal College Education Gidan Madi, Sokoto state. Therefore, the research will tremendously benefit the College administration who responsible for the overall success of the College. It will also benefit Library Management who responsible for designing library services in the College. Staff students, and researchers who are the end users of the library service will benefit from the fruits of this work.

Literature review

The study was reviewed under the concepts of Academic libraries, information resources, types of information resources in academic libraries, availability of information resources, accessibility of information resources, utilization of information resources and challenges associated with availability, accessibility and utilization of information resources. Knowing that the library includes the totality of human and organized material resources available in both books and non-books formats for providing and obtaining needed information. Academic libraries are attached to tertiary institutions supporting the mission of their parent institutions which is teaching and research by providing required reading materials in all formats. Bizi & Liman (2023) identified, e-journals, e-newspapers, Online Public Access Catalogue (OPAC), CD-ROM databases, e-books, online databases, e-research reports, virtual library, science direct online, as well as Ebscohost reference databases as the types of academic e-resources. Popoola (2008) affirmed that the

information resources and services available in institutional information systems must be capable of supporting research activities among the students and faculty members. Dickson (2006) reported that the availability of printed resources, computers and electronic resources were among the reasons for undergraduate students' usage of academic libraries and this recorded 58% of responses each. Uдах & Ntui (2015) revealed that there was a significant influence of Accessibility to text book on the utilization of library resources by teachers. It was generally concluded that accessibility to library resources significantly influenced the utilization of library resources by teachers in secondary schools. Oyewusi and Oyeboade (2009) studied the accessibility and use of library resources by undergraduate students found out that library was highly used by undergraduate students for their academics. Malarvizhi and Sarangapani (2016) have carried out a study with an aim to first evaluate the usage of electronic information resources by the faculty members of Karunya University, Coimbatore. It was revealed that library resources significantly influenced the utilization of library resources. Yakubu A.Y. & Onuoah J. (2021) identified a number of challenges that was commonly which include slow internet speed, struggle in finding related information, surplus of information on the Internet, slow speed of the internet affected the speed at which information is retrieved, limited computer system, power outage, lack of ICT skills, insufficient Database in Economics education, Inadequate user ability in manipulating e-resources, expensive internet subscriptions, limited access to e-resources, and poor networking system. Mahwasane & Mudzielwana (2016) reveal that there are challenges such as for example, lack of proper knowledge on how to use information retrieval skills, insufficient user education, lack of computer knowledge, Information Communication Technology (ICT) in accessing information in the library.

Methodology

This study adopted descriptive research that used survey research design. According to Kumar, (2014) descriptive survey research design is a procedure where a researcher asks questions and scaled the respondents' opinions in an appropriate rating scale. The study used quantitative research method as it investigates phenomena by collecting numerical data which are further

***Corresponding Author: Saleh Hussaini (June) 2024**

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analyzed mathematically (Statistically). One great advantage of using this research is to give justification for the approach used in the research.

Summary of Major Findings of the Study

Response rate indicates that out of 155 questionnaires administered (142) 91.61% responded, this is a great achievement. 89.33% (67) of the students were potential users of the library only 10% (8) denied the use of the library as shown in Table 4.1.

Table 4.2 showed that the number of students sample of 75 were picked randomly from each department around the school. The gender depicted 62.66% (47) male students and 29.33% (22) female students, 8 didn't respond.

The highest frequency age range is 57 of 20 - 30 class interval. The lowest is within the class interval of 51 - 60. Majority of the respondents believe that there are available information resources in print. Few did not respond. 50 of the students as the majority said no to the availability of information resources, only few agreed that there is availability of printed information resources. 32% (24) of the students use the library for assignments, 26.66% (20) for personal research, 18.66% (14) for school project, 9.33% (7) for current happenings and 13.33% (10) for relaxation.

26.66% (20) find it difficult to access information resources, 13.33% (10) don't, and majority 60% (45) didn't respond, this makes it difficult to interpret. 25 agreed the resources available in the library are outdated, 15 argued and 35 did not respond, 15 agreed that there are insufficient information resources, 15 argued and 35 did not respond. 10 agreed the environment is un conducive, 25 disagree and 40 did not respond. 35 users agreed there is lack of computer skills, 25 argued and 15 didn't respond. 10 agreed to bad treatment from the library staff, 40 argued and 25 did not respond. Poor or unstable electricity 29 agreed, 25 argued and 21 did not respond. slow/poor Internet connectivity speed: 24 agreed 16 disagreed 35 did not respond. 30 agreed to limited computer systems, 25 disagreed and 20 did not respond. 25 agreed to limited seats and other fittings, 25 argued and 25 did not respond.

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Staff: the findings of the potential users of staff members of Gidan Madi College Library showed 60 users and 7 denying the use of the library. All the staff members are splitted within the sections with school of vocational and technology carrying the highest percentage of 22.38 and the lowest being 7.46% splitted within registry, Administrative, library and ICT respectively. Male staff members take the highest number of staff members followed by female staff members with 10 staff members, 7 did not respond. The highest number of staff members at 47.76% are within the age range of 31-40 which makes them the modal of the population sample of the staff members. The median falls in 41-50 with 14.92% and the minimum number of staff member within the age range is 61-70 with the percentage of 1.49%. The most available printed information resources are books with 97.01% (65), followed by journals with 89.55% (60), the minimum printed resources are gazettes with 44.77% (30). The staff members opined lack of e-information resources with 44.7% (30) "NO" response and 35.82% (24) "YES" response. Base on the findings of accessibility of Printed information resources in the College Library, majority of 52.23%(35) of the staff members believe that there is a very low service of accessibility for books in the library, only 16.41%(11) of staff members are very satisfied with their accessibility services, 4.47%(3) is the lowest with dissatisfactory, 11.94(8) consider it average. This indicates that there is a low service provision in the library. Websites has the highest percentage of highly dissatisfactory with 37.31% (25), and minimum of 7.46% (5) highly satisfactory. E-theses/dissertations has the lowest percentage with 14.92% (10) highly dissatisfactory and 5.97% (4) strongly satisfied. 52.23% (35) did not respond. Therefore a conclusion cannot be drawn on the findings.

On the challenges associated with availability Accessibility and utilization of the information resources in the library is that, majority of staff chose "NO" to difficulty in finding relevant information resources with the percentages of 65.67%(44), only 29.85%(20) agreed to the difficulties. 44.77% (30) was the lowest percentage of "NO" option for unconducive environment and lack of ICT. Outdated resources and bad treatment from library assistants have the lowest percentage with 74.62% (50) each.

Table 4.1 Respond rate

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STAFF

Respondents	Number of Questionnaires administered	Number of valid questionnaires returned	Percentage
Staff	75	67	89%

Table 4.2: Gender of Staff

Male	45	67.16
Female	22	32.83
Total	67	100

Table 4.5: Potential user of Gidan Madi College Library

School of Education	9	13.43%
School of Vocational and Technology	15	22.38%
School of Science	13	19.40%
Bursary	10	14.92%
Registry	5	7.46%
Administrative	5	7.46%
Library	5	7.46%
ICT	5	7.46%
Total	67	100%

Students

Respondents	Number of Questionnaires administered	Number of valid questionnaires returned	Percentage
Students	80	75	93.7%

S/N	Question	Frequency	Percentage
1	School of Education	38	50.66%
2	School of Vocational & Technology	17	22.66%
3	School of Science	20	26.66%
	Total	75	100%

Table 4.2: Gender of students

Male	47	62.66
Female	22	29.33
No response	6	8
Total	75	100

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Table 4.3: Age range Student Respondents

Age interval	Frequency	Percentage %
20 – 30	57	76
31 – 40	10	13.33
41 – 50	3	4
51 – 60	5	6.66
Total	75	100\

Table 4.4: Challenges encounter while accessing and using the information resources in your library

Difficulty in finding relevant information	20	10	45
Outdated resources	25	15	35
Insufficient information resources	15	15	45
In conducive environment	10	25	40
Lack of ICT SKILLS	35	25	15
Bad treatment from library assistants	10	40	25
Poor or unstable electricity	29	25	21
Slow/poor Internet connectivity speed	24	16	35
Limited computer systems	30	25	20
Limited seats and others fittings	25	25	25
Others	27	23	25

Conclusions

The findings revealed that, majority of the students with 66.66% (50) agreed that there are no available information resources in the library. Staff members on the other hand agreed there are available printed resources and disagreed with the availability of e-resources with 44.7(30). Accessibility: majority of the students being 60% (44) did not respond which makes it difficult to conclude. Hence, 26.66% (20) find it difficult to access the information resources. The staff members expressed highly dissatisfactory on website accessibility with the highest of 37.31% (25).

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Utilization: 32% of the students use the library for their assignments and the rest of the percentage splitted among other related activities including current happenings with the minimum of 9. 33% (7) challenges: there were number of challenges that was identified, commonly which include slow internet speed, difficulty in finding related information, slow speed of the internet, limited computer system, poor/unstable electricity, lack of ICT skills, insufficient Database, Inadequate user ability in manipulating e-resources, limited access to e-resources, and poor networking system.

Recommendations

Based on the investigation, appropriate strategies were suggested to solve the identified challenges, the strategies include:

- ✓ Provision of more current information resources,
- ✓ Adjusting to more friendly classification scheme for the printed resources,
- ✓ An increase in bandwidth,
- ✓ Provision of stable power,
- ✓ Employing trained staff on the ground to assist users on the use of ICT,
- ✓ Organize training and workshops on ICT for fresh students,
- ✓ Provide a more user-friendly platform, first-year students should be introduced to computer training.

Acknowledgments

This research was funded by TETFUND under the Institution Based Research (IBR) Annual Intervention. We would like to express our gratitude to TETFUND for providing the necessary funding and support for this research project. I am confident that the findings of this study will

contribute to the advancement of knowledge in the field of construction materials, job creation and sustainable development in Nigeria. I would like to use this opportunity to appreciate entire management of Federal College of Education Gidan Madi Sokoto state for the opportunity and support to conduct this research.

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